

CoARA Boost Cascade Funding – Call 1

Progress Report

Project	
Project number	24-CoARA-067
Name of the project	Towards a Qualitative Paradigm: Rethinking Research and Researchers Assessment at Blanquerna, Universitat Ramon Llull-ReAss
Type of project	<input type="checkbox"/> Teaming <input type="checkbox"/> Institutional change <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Institutional pilot
Reporting period	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> M0 – M6 <input type="checkbox"/> M7 – M12
Reporting deadline	June 25th, 2025
Date of last update of the report	June 25 th , 2025

Organisation	
Organisation name	Contact
Please fill-in information in red for Teaming Project's coordinator	Name, mail address
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1. Purpose of the CoARA Cascade Funding Progress Report

The CoARA Cascade Funding Progress Report serves as a tool for supporting beneficiaries of the program in sharing progress with the CoARA Secretariat, and, upon request, the European Commission. It provides a framework to track progress, monitor activities, and bring transparency in how resources are used during the reporting period.

Additionally, the template facilitates continual reflection and documentation of the projects, allowing for a comprehensive overview of their activities, achievements.

For Teaming projects, please note that one Progress Report is expected per project.

Please note that this monitoring report template covers the technical aspect of the progress reporting and that the Excel table “Project Budget template” covers the financial part. Please fill in the Excel table according to your type of project:

- Annex 4 - for mono-beneficiary (i.e., Institutional Pilot Calls and Institutional Change Calls):

<https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2025/02/Projects-budget-template-unique-partner-1.xlsx>

OR

- Annex 5 - for partnering projects (i.e., Teaming Calls – each partner must complete one sheet in the document):

<https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2025/02/Projects-budget-template-partnering-projects-1.xlsx>

Both documents are mandatory and expected to be submitted to complete the reporting milestones in M06 and M12.

Please send back your report, your use of resources (Excel budget table) and your annexes (if applicable) by June 25th, 2025, to secretariat@coara.eu

2. Monitoring system

To ensure easy monitoring of the progress made in the funded projects, the monitoring system consists of the following parts:

- Progress measurement base (section 2.1.)
- Progress reporting (section 2.2.)
- Dissemination activities (section 2.3)
- Next Steps (section 2.4)
- Budget Monitoring (section 2.5)

2.1. Progress measurement base: Work plan

Please provide a hyperlink or summary of your work plan for the **M0 – M6 period** in the box below.

Month 1-2: Planning and Resource Allocation

We will form a steering committee including the research and quality vice-deans, the research institutes directors and a representative of each of the researcher career stages. The committee will allocate the budget and staff capacity. We will design focus groups and workshops to communicate the pilot plan and ask for researchers' collaboration. **KPI Milestone: Steering committee announced M1 Deliverable: Steering committee members. Resources Plan. Use of resources 0.2 PM**

Month 3-4: Review of Current Practices

We will conduct an internal review (focus group, interviews and survey) to collect the researchers views and feedback regarding the current assessment practices and the most urgent challenges that need to be addressed.

In parallel, we will review the current assessment system. Since 2019, Blanquerna has developed a research assessment system based on a mixed set of qualitative and quantitative criteria. It includes a portfolio, which probably can be adapted to the new criteria and a table collecting all the publications and competitive research projects. The research positive assessment allows researchers to move forward in their careers and maintain their allocated research time. However, based on the current documents, the positive assessment highly relies on the quality metrics of the publications, measured through the IF and the journal position in well-known rankings. The number of such publications, combined with the number of projects and the amount of funding obtained is the second criteria of relevance to have a positive evaluation. Modifying these quantitative criteria will imply revising all the biases and underlying assumptions that are operating in the current assessment system accepted by researchers at all career stages as objective. This will also require to raise researchers and other university stakeholders' awareness regarding the CoARA principles and the ARRA agreement to which our Spanish University has committed.

Once the review of the current system and practices as well as researchers' perspectives has been collected and structured, we will develop an internal site including the results, the challenges to

address, as well as the next steps to develop. The site will be interactive and collect FAQ and suggestions from researchers to co-create new assessment criteria. **KPI Milestone 100 Practices reviewed M4 Deliverable: ReAss best practices identified. Use of resources 0.5 PM**

Month 5-6: Development of New Criteria

Based on the CoARA principles and the issues highlighted by the researcher community at Blanquerna, we will develop new qualitative assessment criteria. These criteria will be discussed first with the Steering committee and then with the Blanquerna researchers in several workshops to adjust it to the characteristics of our research fields: Psychology, health, education and sport.

The new criteria and tools will be piloted with a small group of researchers representative of all the research fields. **KPI Milestone ReAss criteria identified M5 Deliverable: ReAss methodology criteria Use of resources 0.75 PM**

2.2. Progress reporting

This section aims to facilitate reporting of progress for all projects, and coordination of partners for Teaming projects.

2.2.1. Reporting process

The table and text boxes below provide a simplified method to report on projects' progress quantitatively and qualitatively. Please add as many rows as required.

Outputs/ Deliverables/ Activity	Brief description	Its relevance to <u>ARRA</u> <u>commitments</u> Which commitment is addressed and how?	Hyperlink to final version if available	Timeframe MM/YY	Funding acknowledgment (if available)
Steering committee constitution	Formal constitution of the SC (kick off meeting)	5, 10	-	M 1-2	No
Report of current practices	Review of current practices undertaken at the Faculty for research activity assessment made by the SC	5, 6	Report	M 3-4-5	Yes
Researcher's opinion data collection	Researchers' opinions gathered through a survey	1, 2, 7, 10	Results Report	M 5-6	Yes
<i>Report of new assessment items</i>	Design of new items aimed to assess research practices based on CoARA principles and taking into consideration researchers' opinions	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6	In process	M 6, 7	Yes

Please make sure that funding acknowledgement is added to all your publications.

Please link your publications/outputs in the following Zenodo community "[CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Beneficiaries](#)". For support, please refer to the guidelines in Annex 1.

Please use the following title format to name your documents: "CoARA Boost CFI – [Acronym of the project/3 first words of your project title] – [Document title]"

Example (fictive): CoARA Boost CFI – COSMOS – Booklet for Strategic Meeting”

2.2.2. Narrative assessment of progress

Period 1 - reporting deadline: June 25th, 2025

The narrative assessment of progress should detail current progress, including successes and hurdles encountered during implementation of the workplan.

If your project is organised in WPs, please mention the title and give a summary of work/tasks conducted in each.

Please detail your progress’ narrative assessment in the box below.

Month 1-3: Planning and Resource Allocation

1) Management structure and dynamics

The *Steering Committee* (SC) has been created, including the research and quality vice-deans (Dr Ana Andrés and Dr Ignaci Cifré), the research institute directors (Dr Montserrat Castelló, Dr Mireia Civis and Dr Xavier Pujadas) and a representative of each of the researcher career stages (Marina García-Morante: ECR; Dr Anna Sala: Mid-Career; Dr Sacra Morejon: Senior researcher). Montserrat Casanovas has been appointed as the SC officer. The committee allocated the budget and staff capacity. We have also designed the focus groups and workshops to communicate the pilot plan and solicit the collaboration of researchers.

The *Steering Committee* (SC) has appointed the *Executive Committee* (EC) as responsible for operationalising and implementing the specific activities outlined in the work plan. The EC includes the Psychology Research Institute, Dr Montserrat Castelló, who also leads the *CoARA Re-Ass project*, the research vice-dean, Dr Ana Andrés, and representatives from each stage of the researcher's career: Marina García-Morante, Dr Anna Sala, and Dr Sacra Morejon.

Finally, an *Advisory Board* (AB) has been established to monitor, support, and endorse (when necessary) the SC's decisions. Such AB includes the Dean, the academic vice-dean and the secretary of the Facultat de Psicologia, Ciències de l'Educació I de l'Esport (FPCEE) (Dr Marc Franco, Dr Montserrat Prats and Dr Marc Llinás), the head of the FPCEE library and responsible for research data repositories, as well as the Universitat Ramon Llull vice-chancellor (Dr Jordi Teixidó) and the Research unit coordinator (Anna Caellas).

2) Planning and resource allocation

The two committees (SC and EC) and the *Advisory Board* (AB) were established during the project kick-off in February, where the initial work plan schedule was discussed and adjusted. We had to postpone the meeting due to the unexpected new appointment of the research vice-dean, which was not anticipated when the *Re-Ass project* was submitted. The new vice-dean, Ana Andrés, began her term in February, which explains the schedule adjustment that prevented the kick-off meeting from being held earlier.

After discussing the task characteristics and workload requirements, the AB allocated the necessary resources for the staff included in the SC and EC according to their responsibilities.

Month 3-6: Review of Current Practices

3) Analysis of the current system

Background

The Faculty of Psychology, Education and Sport Sciences (FPCEE) has a long-standing tradition of evaluating the research activity of its academic staff, beginning with the publication of its first evaluation criteria and procedures in October 2004. Evaluation—covering both teaching and research—is structured in three-year cycles. The first evaluation covered the period from September 2004 to August 2007, although internal circumstances delayed its actual implementation.

The process was reactivated following the May 2010 publication of the institutional framework for academic career progression. The evaluation period was extended to September 2010, and the assessment focused exclusively on faculty members with officially recognized research time in their contracts. In 2010, 58 faculty members were assessed: 51% received a positive evaluation, 30% negative, and 19% did not submit the required documentation. In March 2013, a second round of evaluations was conducted using the same criteria, with an exemption introduced for those who had already undergone external evaluation by a recognized quality agency (e.g., doctoral defense, academic accreditation, or recognized research periods). Of the 69 eligible faculty members, 56% were evaluated positively, 22% negatively, and 22% were exempt. Additional evaluations were conducted in 2016 and 2019, maintaining similar procedures and yielding comparable results.

Unified Evaluation Criteria

In preparation for the 2024–2029 General Research Plan (Pla General de recerca- PGR) uniting the three Blanquerna faculties, a joint reflection process was initiated on how to evaluate academic research activity. While FPCEE had previously conducted four rounds of evaluation, the faculties of Health Sciences and of Communication and International Relations had not. The process began by reviewing other universities' models and was designed to align with the qualitative and quantitative standards used by quality assurance agencies to evaluate both researchers and research centers both in Catalonia and Spain. The primary goal was to establish common evaluation standards across the three faculties, while respecting the specificity of their academic disciplines.

Development Process

The work began in February 2021 with the Vice-Deans of Research from all three faculties. A preliminary draft was shared with the Directors of Research Institutes, amended accordingly, and then submitted for approval by the Blanquerna Research Strategic Council (CER). Though the PGR was not formally approved until January 2024, the CER agreed to pilot the new evaluation system at FPCEE in 2023, continuing the established three-year cycle. The pilot covered the period from October 1, 2019, to September 30, 2022. This pilot helped calibrate scoring thresholds for each contractual academic profile across faculties. Prior to launching the pilot, all research group leaders at the faculty were briefed to clarify the new criteria. Once validated, the evaluation system was also implemented at the other two faculties.

Evaluation as a Quality Indicator

Research and quality are intrinsically linked. Research enhances methodological rigor, while quality assessment ensures that scientific production is appropriate and recognized. For the most recent evaluation, the process was jointly implemented by the Research Office and the Faculty's

Quality Unit, to ensure alignment with the evaluation of teaching activities traditionally managed by the latter.

Purpose of the Evaluation

The assessment targeted faculty members with officially recognized research time. It aimed to stimulate research activity, support career development strategies, and maintain quality standards required by external agencies. Two secondary goals emerged:

- The need to provide evidence helped to uncover achievements not previously reported through regular channels (e.g., the MERIT platform or research funding tracking).
- The validation process allowed for pedagogical correction of misreported records.

The evaluation tool was also designed as a self-assessment instrument, allowing academics to measure their research achievements against their professional category's expectations, even though formal evaluations will continue to follow the three-year cycle.

Evaluation Criteria

The assessment was based on three categories:

- Productivity (60% weight): Impact-factor publications (JCR, SJR), books or chapters (SPI), other publications, dissemination activities (conference presentations, peer review, editorial boards), and contributions like doctoral supervision and patents.
- Projects (35%): Leadership or participation in competitive and non-competitive projects, with recognition also given to unsuccessful competitive proposals.
- Other merits (5%): Research group leadership and research stays (minimum one month).

A standardized form was created to collect personal data, quantitative metrics for each category, and qualitative tables to justify evidence submitted. Guidelines and templates accompanied the call.

Validation Process

Evaluation was also intended as a formative exercise. Alongside scores, individualized feedback addressed issues in submitted evidence. Validation was supported by technical staff from the Library Service (publications), Research Office (research projects), and Innovation and Transfer Office (transfer projects). A shared validation spreadsheet facilitated annotations and corrections.

Results

Only faculty members with recognized research time were required to participate; others could opt in voluntarily. A differentiated scoring threshold was applied based on contract type. In the latest call, 80 researchers participated, with 20% exempt due to external evaluation credentials. Of the remaining 64, 43% received a “very favorable” evaluation, 42% “favorable,” and 14% “unfavorable.”

Feedback

Each researcher received personalized feedback via email, including:

- Overall rating (very favorable, favorable, or not favorable)
- Score out of 100
- Average and score range for their academic category
- The scoring table for each evaluation parameter

Where applicable, feedback included detailed explanations of corrections and contact details for follow-up with the validating departments.

Documents and Tools Used

- Annexe 1. Call for applications
- Annexe 2. Evaluation form template
- Annexe 3. Table completion guide
- Annexe 4. Scoring table with categories, parameters, metrics, values, and caps
- Annexe 5. Final scoring thresholds
- Annexe 6. Individual evaluation report template

4) *Researchers' perceptions of the current practices*

We have developed and applied a survey including both open-ended and scaled-response items to collect the researchers' views and feedback regarding the current assessment practices and the most urgent challenges that need to be addressed (see Annexe 7). The survey has been emailed to 200 researchers from all career stages. After two reminders, 26 answers have been collected until now. We plan a new iteration of the survey at the beginning of September after the summer break.

The open-ended responses have been thematically analysed, structured around five dimensions: strengths, weaknesses, challenges, risks, and opportunities (SWOT analysis). Within each dimension, emergent categories were built from the data. Moreover, the results have been distributed into four groups considering the HRS4R profiles (R1 new researchers; R2 recognized researchers; R3 consolidated researchers; R4 leading researchers). From the survey results we identified perceived strengths—such as the system's standardisation, formative purpose, and institutional follow-up—as well as significant weaknesses. These include limited criteria diversification, inadequate support, bureaucratic overload, and failure to recognise key research activities like knowledge transfer and social impact. The survey also reveals opportunities for system reform, including the adoption of more inclusive, flexible, and co-created evaluation frameworks. However, threats such as metric-driven pressures, cultural resistance, and risks to institutional prestige are also noted. Recommendations focus on promoting equity, transparency, and relevance in research evaluation, with specific emphasis on financial support, criteria co-construction, and interdisciplinary recognition (the complete results report can be checked in Annexe 8). Moreover, participants in the survey have been invited to be part of the pilot assessment we will conduct next November. All 26 have agreed and we envisage to recruit more voluntary participants with the September survey new iteration.

5) *ReAss best practices identified*

We have allocated a specific space to the Re-Ass project within the [FPCEE Research internal site](#). All the faculty have access to this site, and we began to publish the activities, and the results obtained so far, as well the focus group meetings, workshops and other initiatives planned to raise awareness among the researchers about the Re-Ass aims and CoAra principles. The site is interactive and collects FAQ and suggestions from researchers to co-create new assessment criteria.

We are currently still in the process of sharing these results with the researcher community to raise awareness and co-creating the new assessment criteria.

Month 5-6: Development of New Criteria

6) Results of the research assessment system analysis

The analysis of the current research assessment system has been done by critically contrasting the results regarding the procedures, documents and strategies, as well as the researchers' perceptions with the objectives of the Re-Ass project and the CoARA principles. A SWOT analysis was applied to identify the major strengths, weaknesses, risks, challenges, and opportunities of the current practices. Results are summarised below (the complete report can be checked in Annexe 9).

Strengths

a) Institutionalization and Continuity

- A long-standing tradition of regular, structured evaluations (since 2004) has institutionalized assessment as part of academic culture.
- The triennial cycle provides a consistent framework for faculty career development and accountability.

b) Structured and Transparent Procedures

- Defined criteria communicated through templates and guides ensures conceptual transparency.
- Clear communication through individualized feedback and engagement of technical services ensures procedural transparency.

c) Integration of Quality Assurance Structures

- Collaboration between the Research Office and the Quality Unit strengthens coherence between teaching and research evaluations.

d) Recent Moves Towards Unification and Reflection

- Efforts to develop unified criteria across all faculties reflect institutional commitment to improving consistency.

e) Formative aim of the research evaluation

- Feedback mechanisms offer developmental support for researchers, including correction of misreported evidence and learning opportunities

Weaknesses

a) Heavy Dependence on Quantitative Indicators

- High weight on bibliometric criteria (JCR/SJR, IF) and competitive funding metrics reinforces a productivity-based culture, contrary to CoARA principles.

b) Limited Recognition of Diverse Contributions

- Other forms of impact (societal, collaborative, open science practices) are marginal or missing in the current framework.

c) Rigid Scoring Model

- Top-down metrics (fixed scores, caps) may not accommodate disciplinary diversity or career stage differences, potentially disadvantaging early-career researchers or interdisciplinary work.

d) *Partial Coverage*

- Only researchers with officially recognized research hours are evaluated mandatorily. This may exclude relevant contributions from other academics, hindering a holistic understanding of the institution's research landscape.

e) *Limited Peer Involvement and Reflective Dialogue*

- While technical validation is robust, there is little indication of peer-review processes or reflexive discussion on what constitutes 'quality' research

Opportunities

- a) *Fostering Researcher Development*: A new model can better support researchers' career progression, especially in under-recognized areas like collaborative, practice-based or societal research.
- b) *Innovation and Inclusion*: Creating new assessment tools (e.g., narrative CVs, open peer feedback, impact narratives) should help us to foster inclusion, innovation and recognize the complexity of research work.
- c) *Interdisciplinary and Societal Impact Recognition*: Expanding criteria can help reward activities central to Blanquerna's mission—engaged, transformative research in education, health, and communication.

Threats

- a) *Resistance to Reform*: Shifting away from long-established metric-based assessment may meet cultural or political resistance, especially from researchers benefiting from the current model.
- b) *Credibility Gaps*: Without robust communication and legitimacy-building efforts, the new system may be perceived as less objective or more discretionary.
- c) *Loss of Benchmarking Ease*: Moving from metric-based scores to qualitative evaluation may hinder comparisons at the institutional or external levels unless new tools are developed.

Synthesis of the SWOT analysis

The current system at Blanquerna combines administrative robustness and historical continuity with a strong emphasis on quantitative, metric-based assessment. While it ensures procedural consistency and aligns with traditional quality assurance standards, it underrepresents the full diversity of scholarly contributions. It rewards a narrow definition of excellence, primarily favoring high-impact publications and competitive funding, with limited sensitivity to disciplinary differences, career stages, or alternative forms of impact. These limitations pose risks to fairness, inclusivity, and innovation. Moreover, while formative purposes were claimed to be crucial, the existing procedures, strategies, tools and mechanisms have resulted in limited evidence of how they promote researcher development. Significant aspects of the Co-Ara principles proposed by Re-Ass have been absent of the research assessment practices (e.g. valuing qualitative assessment, peer review, narrative accounts, and a broader spectrum of research contributions). Considering the mentioned strengths of the current system, we should warrant careful navigation of cultural resistance, institutional coherence, and methodological clarity. In parallel, three major challenges need to be addressed:

- a) *Raising awareness of the Co-Ara principles as a new Assessment Culture*: We aim to transition from quantification and rankings to reflective, qualitative assessments. We knew

that this transition requires deep cultural change and strategic engagement. Re-Ass training and dissemination strategies must carefully address these requirements.

- b) *Ensuring Fairness and Transparency*: Qualitative assessment methods must be clearly justified and consistently applied to ensure perceived fairness. We are already working on new templates that can appropriately replace the existing ones (see Annexes)
- c) *Accommodating Disciplinary and Career Diversity*: This was a non-solved challenge in the existing model and current practices. The Re-Ass new model should provide mechanisms to remain sensitive to different research profiles while preserving shared standards.

7) *Developing new criteria. ReAss dimensions of change*

The first step towards the development of new criteria has included the agreement regarding the dimensions that will drive the discussion about the criteria and structure the strategies and actions to develop in the pilot. We ended-up with the following six dimensions of change (see Annexe 9):

1. *Broaden the conceptualization of Research Quality*
The new proposal will foster the problematization of the concepts of research assessment and research quality by discussing the current systems assumptions, strengths and weaknesses and acknowledging diverse outputs and impact types, including community engagement, open science, interdisciplinary work, and knowledge transfer.
2. *Embed Peer Review and Narrative Assessment*
The new proposal will develop clear procedures and tools for qualitative, peer-based evaluation and introduce narrative CVs or portfolios tailored to Blanquerna's research fields.
3. *Ensure researcher development and inclusivity Across Career Stages*
The proposal will discuss with the researcher community at Blanquerna how to include flexible, transparent benchmarks that consider researcher development, supporting early-career researchers and non-traditional trajectories. At the same time, this dimension will discuss ways to address the tension between team and collaborative research work and individual development by considering the research activity structures and roles at Blanquerna and URL.
4. *Enhance Reflexivity and Transparency*
Similarly, the proposal will provide procedures to ensure formative feedback, dialogic assessment practices, and clear criteria to ensure legitimacy and trust.
5. *Foster Researcher Engagement and Co-Creation*
Ultimately, the proposal will sustain ongoing consultation and training with researchers to co-create the new criteria and raise awareness of the rationale behind the reform.
6. *Discuss the Role of Evaluation in Career Progression*
Though this is a long-term dimension of change that exceeds the Re-Ass objectives, we also want to start the discussion regarding how assessment outcomes influence recognition, research time allocation, and promotion within a framework consistent with CoARA.

2.3. Dissemination activities

Include in this section where your project information was disseminated or if outputs achieve impact.

Please add as many rows as required.

Name Please specify the type of activity (e.g. webinar, presentations' slides, ...)	Link	Target audience
Workshop addressing researcher career development	Workshop January 2024	Doctoral supervisors
Presentation slides to discuss the current research assessment system	Internal presentation February 2025	Research teams and projects PIs at the FPCEE
Seminars to analyse current research assessment system and discuss its alignment with the CoAra principles.	March, April, May and June 2025	Research Institutes leaders at the FPCEE
Online survey aiming to collect academics and researchers' opinions about current practices at the Faculty on research assessment	Link to the online survey	All academics and researchers from the Faculty
Research meeting lead by the Vice-Dean of Research, aiming to share the results obtained during the first phase of the project (slides presentation)	Upcoming meeting on 10 th July	Principal investigators (PI) of the research groups
Meeting lead by the Steering Committee (SC) aiming to share the new criteria with PI (slides presentation and report)	Upcoming meeting on early September (between the 10 th and the 15 th)	Principal investigators (PI) of the research groups and project leaders
Meeting lead by the SC aiming to share the new criteria and assessment procedure with participants of the pilot study (slides presentation and report)	Upcoming meeting on mid-September (before the 20 th)	Academics and researchers participating in the assessment pilot study
Assessment feedback given to participants (individualised report)	Mid November	Academics and researchers participating in the assessment pilot study
Presentation of the pilot procedure and results to the rest of the Blanquerna faculties	End of November	Researchers through all the career stages from faculties of health, Education, Sport Sciences and Information Sciences
Round of dissemination presentations of the pilot procedure and results to the	From 1 st to the 15 th of December	Deans and vice-deans councils as well as the ethics and Doctorate committees from URL

Universitat Ramon Llull -URL-community		
Series of Workshops addressed to URL researchers	From 1 st to the 15 th of December	Disciplinary and cross-disciplinary workshops to raise awareness on the Co-ARA principles and promote engagement with the new assessment criteria and procedures

2.4. Next steps

The “next steps” section should detail future actions, including activities and decisions, to be taken and/or implemented to achieve the project.

Please describe the **future action and activities planned for the M7 – M12 period** in the box below.

Month 7-8: Development of New Criteria

Based on the results from the focus-groups, seminars, documents and the survey applied, we have already started to develop the new qualitative assessment criteria. These criteria will be discussed first with the Steering committee and Advisory Board (beginning of September) and then with the Blanquerna researchers in several workshops (September and October) to adjust them to the characteristics of our research fields: Psychology, health, education and sport.

The new criteria and tools will be piloted with a small group of researchers representative of all the research fields (October and November). **KPI Milestone ReAss criteria identified M5**

Deliverable: ReAss methodology criteria Use of resources 0.75 PM

Month 7-9: Training and Awareness Raising

We will develop and deliver a series of training programs, both online and face-to-face to raise awareness on the criteria benefits as well as on their alignment with CoARA principles and guidelines., mainly during September and October 2025. Moreover, we will organize workshops and seminars with the Institutes Research Directors -EGER and the Steering Committee to develop the appropriate tools to be used in the pilot assessment (October). **KPI Milestone 10 workshops delivered M8 Deliverable: ReAss training report. Use of resources 0.75 PM**

Month 9-10: Implementation

The new assessment criteria will be implemented across the institute on a voluntary basis with a representative group of researchers across all the career stages and disciplinary research fields. At the moment, 26 researchers have already committed to be part of the pilot (mainly R3 and R4). We will apply new recruitment strategies next September and October to enhance this number and ensure other research stages representativeness (R1 and R2). A group of trainers and assessors will be created among the members of the SC and AB as well as among the Research Institutes Directors. They will receive training for them to explain the pilot assessment project to their peers

in each Faculty. **KPI Milestone ReAss criteria implemented at Blanquerna M10 Deliverable ReAss implementation report. Use of resources 1.5 PM**

Month 11: Monitoring and Feedback

We will collect feedback from all the participants through surveys and focus group and monitor effectiveness of the new assessment proposal. Based on the feedback results, we will make the necessary adjustments on the proposal considering all career stages and disciplinary research fields. **KPI Milestone Reass monitoring implemented M11 Deliverable ReAss monitoring report. Use of resources 0.6 PM**

Month 12: Evaluation and Reporting

We will develop specific tools to evaluate the impact of the new criteria (Focus group, Delphi groups and surveys). Once analysed the evaluation results, we will prepare and share a report on outcomes and recommendations. **KPI Milestone ReAss pilot validated M12 Deliverable ReAss evaluation report. Use of resources 0.5 PM**

2.5. Budget monitoring

Please note that this Monitoring Report template covers the technical aspect of the progress reporting and that the Excel table “Project Budget template” covers the financial part. Please fill in the Excel table according to your type of project:

- Annex 4 – for mono-beneficiary (i.e., Institutional Pilot Calls and Institutional Change Calls):

<https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2025/02/Projects-budget-template-unique-partner-1.xlsx>

OR

- Annex 5 – for partnering projects (i.e., Teaming Calls – each partner must complete one sheet in the document):

<https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2025/02/Projects-budget-template-partnering-projects-1.xlsx>

Both documents are mandatory and expected to be submitted to complete the reporting milestones in M06 and M12.

Annex 1 – Guidelines for CoARA signatories on uploading outputs files to the CoARA community on Zenodo

Step 1: Accessing Zenodo

Go to the Zenodo website: <https://zenodo.org/>

Sign in to your Zenodo account using your credentials. If you do not have an account, you can create one by following the registration process.

Step 2: Uploading Your Outputs/Publications

From your Zenodo dashboard, click on the "Upload" button. Choose "Publication" from the content types.

1. **Select the output/publication file** from your computer that you wish to upload. Ensure that your file is in an appropriate format (e.g., PDF, Word document).
2. **Fill in the required metadata**, including title, authors, description, and keywords. Please ensure that you mention "CoARA" in the keywords for easy identification.
3. **For the "DOI,"** you can choose to either:
 - Leave it blank if you don't have a specific DOI in mind and click "Reserve DOI" if you would like one to be auto-generated for this submission.
 - If you have a DOI that you would like to associate with this submission, enter it in the provided field.
4. **Under "Communities," select "CoARA Boost Cascade Funding beneficiaries"** to associate your upload with our community.
5. **Review the licensing options** and select the one that aligns with your preferences for sharing and reuse.
6. **Click Save and Publish** to submit your file.

Step 3: Notify CoARA Secretariat

Please send an email to secretariat@coara.eu once you have uploaded your output/publication. Include the title and DOI of your upload for easy reference.

Note: If you have multiple versions of the output/publication, we kindly ask you to create a new version on Zenodo rather than uploading separate files.